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Research Article

**IMPACT OF STRUCTURED TEACHING PROGRAM ON
KNOWLEDGE OF MENOPAUSAL PROBLEMS AND ITS
REMEDIES AMONG MENOPAUSAL WOMEN**¹Anam Mohi ud din, ²Rukhsana Bibi¹Rukhsanashaheen892@gmail.com, ²Anammdin@gmail.com**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Women experience a number of significant physiological and psychological changes during their entire life. Menopause is the permanent cessation of menstruation that marks the end of reproductive cycle of a woman. It is a natural phenomenon and women should understand numerous symptoms that affect the quality of life of a woman. The aim of current study is to find the effectiveness of a planned teaching program on knowledge of menopausal women about menopausal problems and its remedies.

Methods: One group pretest-posttest design was used. This interventional study was carried out on 63 menopausal women between 41- 60 years of age in a rural community of Lahore, Pakistan. Sample was collected through convenient sampling technique. The data was collected through structured questionnaire and analyzed on SPSS using descriptive statistics.

Results: In pretest, all women have poor knowledge regarding menopausal problems and its remedies. Knowledge of menopausal women gained after administration of structured teaching program. The results of paired t-test showed a remarkable difference in the pre and post interventional knowledge scores of women ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Educational intervention program was effective in enhancing the knowledge of women regarding menopausal problems and its remedies.

Keywords: Structured Teaching Program, Knowledge, Menopausal Women, Menopause Problems, Remedies.

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INTRODUCTION:

Women are heart of a family as they hold a key position in the shaping of next generation. Women have a significant role in training of healthy lifestyle and pass it to the next generation. Thus, they manage the health of their family members (Moslanejad, Ramezani, & Ghavi, 2014). Women plays a versatile role in her entire life span. During her reproductive years, a woman undergoes a significant number of changes as compared to men (Amin & Kumari, 2016). Women of different age groups cover major percentage of the population; however, they come across some specific problems due to physiological variations in their body such as menopause transition. Menopause is a universal reproductive phenomenon that cannot be avoided (Moslanejad et al., 2014). Menopause can be defined as the period of 12 months of amenorrhea. The effects of menopause on a woman's physical, mental and emotional health are diverse. Menopausal symptoms are common complaints to health practitioners and can affect the quality of life of a woman (Overall, 2017).

As natural menopause is defined as the everlasting termination of menstruation which is the result of the loss of ovarian follicular activity. Natural menopause occurs when a woman missed her periods for 12 consecutive months. It is also considered a new phase in life after the child bearing stage. Menopause represents the end of a woman's reproductive life when there is no additional pathological and physiological etiology can be found (Hautamäki, 2014).

The age of natural menopause is between 46-51 years however it may differ from person to person (Golshiri, Akbari, & Abdollahzadeh, 2016). In Pakistan the average age of menopause is 49.3 years (Mujahid, Siddiqui, & Hussain, 2013). Menopause is considered a normal part of aging when it happens after the age of 40. However, the mean age when the menopause is set to commence is between 50-65 years of age (Bansal, Chaudhary, Soni, & Gupta, 2017).

The menopausal transition is the most complex time where women are at higher risk of developing symptoms like hot flushes, sweating especially at night, musculoskeletal aches, sleep disturbances, shortness of breath, osteoporosis, weight gain, increased facial hair, depression, restlessness, stress, sexual problems, dryness of vagina, and urinary incontinence while laughing and coughing. These symptoms alter women's health and have a significant impact on their biological, psychological, and social health (Peter & Lucita, 2016).

The incidence and prevalence of menopausal symptoms in all over the world is ranging from 40% to 60%, as compared to Asian population that ranged between 10% to 40%. Asian women reported prevalence of fatigue along with muscle and joint aches whereas hot flushes, night sweats, mood swings and psychological symptoms were of less extent among Asians as compared to western women (Bahiyah Abdullah, Moize, Ismail, & Zamri, 2017). Menopause is an important milestone of human life. The prevalence rate of menopausal problems in Pakistan is 39.3%. This percentage shows that social, cultural, psychological and environmental factors has a great influence on experience of menopause. (Sarfaraz, Aamir, Javed, Sarfaraz, & Sarwar, 2015).

There are various remedies used to relieve menopausal symptoms. These include lifestyle modification, hormonal and non-hormonal treatment and various other complementary therapies by the usage of traditional herbs and natural foods (Vanlalnunkimi, 2017). Menopause is considered as natural life event with significant physical and emotional consequences. Many women in developing countries are blind to risks of menopause. Overall, many menopausal women have little knowledge about menopausal issues and their management (Nisar, Sohoo, & Sikandar, 2015).

Most of women in rural areas do not have enough knowledge about preventive measures and remedies to cope with menopausal symptoms (Elkazeh & El-Zeftawy, 2015). All the researches in the field of menopause have also highlighted the importance of education and care for menopausal women to prevent these symptoms. Knowing more about menopause might empower women to better cope with menopausal changes (Devi, Dular, & Yadav, 2015).

Aims Of The Study:

The aim of this study was to see the impact of structured teaching program on knowledge of menopausal women regarding menopausal problems and its remedies.

Significance of the study:

Menopause; a normal phenomenon, occurs around the age of 50 years in the life of a woman. (AlQuaiz, ab Salwa, & Habibac, 2013). All of women around the world face this process and menopausal symptoms affect their health in a number of different ways (Rindner et al., 2017). There is a desire among women for learning about this phase so to improve the quality of life (Anjum, Ghayas, Jahan, & Yasin, 2013). Prevention and management strategies help

menopausal women to maintain their independence and also improve their quality of life (Elkazeh & El-Zeftawy, 2015).

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Menopause is a normal physiological process that indicates the end of reproductive life of a woman as a result of reduced secretions of ovarian hormone. It is commonly known as the “change of life” during which a number of biological and physiological changes appear in the body of a woman (Shijina, 2017). The age of menopause varies from person to person related to a number of factors such as genetic, reproductive history, lifestyle and socioeconomic status. Studies showed that the mean age of menopause varies between 46-50 years. This range of age of menopause is also according to studies from other countries in Asia, such as Indian and Pakistani women experience menopause between 46-49 years (Nisar *et al.*, 2015).

A study was conducted to find the association between knowledge and attitude regarding menopausal care among women in postmenopausal period with their selected demographic variables. The results of this study showed that 86% of the women had inadequate knowledge and some women of them had negative attitude. It also found that there is a need for health education and awareness regarding postmenopausal care and knowledge. Nurses can organize various educational programs to upgrade the knowledge and promote the awareness regarding importance of menopausal care (Sreenivasan, 2018).

Moreover, another study directed to measure the knowledge, attitude and practices of women regarding menopausal health problems. 40% of women were illiterate and they have very poor knowledge about menopausal symptoms. Most common vasomotor symptoms were hot flashes, night sweats, joint pain and abnormal bleeding. This study suggests that most of women thought they do not need any medical assistance. They considered this event as a normal developmental process. It is due to Asian culture that women do not seek any help or treatment unless they suffer with severe symptoms. Women should visit the health centers to increase awareness about menopausal symptoms (Rajbhandari *et al.*, 2017). A study was conducted to assess the awareness of Pakistani women towards menopause. Results showed that dominant part of women was not familiar with the menopausal symptoms and its management. Some women wanted to seek medical treatment to alleviate their symptoms. Counselling and assistance in decision

making is needed to live healthy life (Anjum *et al.*, 2013).

Another research was conducted to assess knowledge of women regarding menopausal problems and its preventive health behaviors. Results showed that majority of women had poor knowledge regarding preventive measures and remedies of menopausal problems. Ninety-four of women had knowledge about menopause and menopausal problems. Thus, the study concluded that there is great need for health personnel to educate women regarding menopausal problems (Elkazeh & El-Zeftawy, 2015). A study revealed that by 20% of women were happy during menopause stage as they were getting freedom from menstruation. A large number of women had a negative impact about menopausal problems because it has had effect on their daily life. Health care personals should educate women about menopause, its symptoms and remedies to assist women to deal effectively with the challenges of menopause (Satpathy, 2016).

According to a study, menopause does not cause any life-threatening conditions, but it affects the quality of life of women. The health care needs of the women vary among different stages of life. However, various remedial measures found to be effective in reducing menopausal symptoms. Women should have basic information about the home care methods or remedies to manage these symptoms effectively (Sreeranjini, 2018). A study reported that menopause has become a major issue of woman's reproductive life. The most common symptoms associated with menopause were joint pain which effect the 64% of women and backache was prevalent among 58% of participants. The less severe problems were insomnia, irritability, hot flushes and depression. Menopausal problems have greatly influenced the life of women. Therefore, it is compulsory to give equal importance to create awareness regarding physical, nutritional, psychosocial and emotional needs of menopausal women. This will enable them to recognize these symptoms early. As a result of early recognition, they will seek intervention or medical help on time. Mass media and other educational interventions for menopausal and post-menopausal women can play a fundamental role to provide knowledge of home management of menopausal issues through diet, exercise, nutritional supplements and health care (Amrita *et al.*, 2017).

A study to assess the impact of educational program among menopausal women depict that there is a positive co-relation between educational programmed and knowledge of participants. The higher percentage

of participants increased their knowledge and management of menopausal problems. Findings showed that there is a positive effect of structured teaching program on knowledge, attitude and practice of menopausal women. Educational programs and interventions has improved their knowledge and health promoting behavior which in turn reduce menopausal symptoms (Nazari, Farmani, Kaveh, & Ghaem, 2016). A quasi experimental study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of teaching program among women of rural area. There was a significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores. Pre-test results showed that women do not have knowledge about menopausal problems. It was observed that post-test knowledge scores were high which demonstrates that administration of structured teaching program improved the knowledge of women. Efforts should be done by health care providers to give education regarding menopausal symptoms and promote their health. It will help them to select coping strategies to overcome the menopausal problems (Amin & Kumari, 2016).

METHODS:

Setting:

The research was conducted in Ali Raza Abad, Raiwind Road Lahore.

Research design:

One group pre-test post-test interventional design was used in this study.

Population:

Menopausal women between 40-50 years of age living in the community of Ali Raza Abad, Raiwind Road, Lahore.

Sampling:

63 women were selected through convenient sampling technique by using Solving's formula.

Research instrument:

A designed questionnaire was used to collect data from the participants.

Data gathering procedure:

Questionnaire was translated into Urdu and were distributed among menopausal women.

Analyze data:

Data was analysed through Statistical Package for the social science (SPSS), 21 version. Descriptive statistics was used to analyse demographic data and inferential statistics was used to analyse the pre and post-test scores of women.

Study timeline:

The study was conducted from September 2018 to December, 2018.

Ethical considerations:

Permission was obtained from IRB (Institutional Review Board) of The University of Lahore.

A written consent was obtained from the participants which was attached with each questionnaire.

The data kept confidential and participants had right to leave the study at any time without any penalty.

RESULTS:

This section presents the outcomes of the study. Age of the participants is shown in Fig 4.1. The mean age of participants was 48.5 years. Other demographic characteristics of 63 subjects are shown in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Description of Demographic Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Respondents	
		Number	Percent
Marital Status	Married	42	66.7
	Widow	13	20.6
	Divorce	8	12.7
Number of Children	Nil	6	9.5
	1-3	25	39.7
	4-6	23	36.5
	More than 6	9	14.3
Type of Family	Nuclear	47	74.6
	Joint	14	22.2
	Extended	1	1.6
Qualification	No Formal Education	32	50.8
	Middle	19	30.2
	Matric	8	12.7
	Inter or more than Inter	4	6.3
Occupation	Self-Business	1	1.6
	House Wife	62	98.4
Monthly Income of family	11,000-15,000	6	9.5
	16,000-20,000	11	17.5
	21,000-25,000	13	20.6
	More than 25,000	33	52.4
Age at Menarche (years)	11-12	9	14.3
	13-14	24	38.1
	Don't Remember	30	47.6
Age at Marriage (years)	16-20	39	61.9
	21-25	23	36.5
	26-30	1	1.6
Family Members had Menopausal Problems	Yes	20	31.7
	No	43	68.3
Previous Source of Information	No	34	53.9
	Electronic Media	8	12.7
	Health Worker	21	33.3
Total		63	100

Pre-interventional knowledge of menopausal women about menopausal problems and its remedies in the form of mean is shown in table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Pre-Interventional Knowledge of Women

Sr No	Knowledge of Menopausal Women	Category	Percentage
1	The word menopause literally means?	Absence of menstruation	41.3
		Suppression of menopause	46.0
		Irregularity in monthly cycle	
		Onset of menstruation	12.7
			0.00
2	The average age of menopause of women is?	45 years	11.1
		48 years	33.3
		50 years	38.1
		55 years	17.5
3	Irregular menstruation prior to menopause is called?	Perimenopause	1.6
		Polymenorrhagia	38.1
		Stoppage of menstruation	1.6
		Dysmenorrhea	58.7
4	Menopause is complete when women do not have a period for about?	6 months	11.1
		8 months	17.5
		10 months	28.6
		12 months	42.9
5	Hormones that helps to control women's menstrual cycle are?	Estrogen and progesterone	3.2
		Thyroid hormone	15.9
		Don't know	69.8
		Oxytocin	11.1
6	The most common acute symptom of menopause is?	Vaginal dryness	39.7
		Hot flushes	15.9
		Fatigue	34.9
		Stressful life events	9.5
7	Hot flush is most pronounced in?	Legs and hands	28.6
		Head and chest	15.9
		Neck and abdomen	39.7
		Toes	15.9
8	Drug which cause more severe and prolonged hot flushes is?	Tamoxifen	1.6
		Paracetamol	31.7
		Mefal spas	9.5
		Don't know	57.1
9	Common symptoms of vaginal dryness include?	Itching	60.3
		Insomnia	7.9
		Weight gain	4.8
		Abdominal pain	27.0
10	Vaginal changes lead to?	Vaginal infection	39.7
		Uterine infection	55.6
		Night sweats	4.8
		None of above	0.00
11	Serious symptom of menopause is?	Hair loss	11.1
		Osteoporosis	55.6
		Digestive problems	4.8
		Allergies	0.00
12	The strong indication of menopausal stage is?	Decrease in sexual desire	28.6

		Decrease in physical activity	66.7
		Increase in physical activity	4.8
		Increase in sexual desire	0.00
13	Cause of menopausal sexual dysfunction is?	Loss of partner	54.0
		Irritability	31.7
		Loss of memory	3.2
		Menopausal changes	11.1
14	One of the reasons for insomnia during menopause is?	Nightmares	30.2
		Hot flush	19.0
		Irrational thinking	50.8
		Memory loss	0.00
15	Leading cause of menopausal depression is?	Anxiety	31.7
		Phobia	4.8
		Stress	4.8
		Tiredness	58.7
16	Risk for depression during menopause is increased due to?	Medication	65.1
		Brain damage	12.7
		Spinal cord surgery	1.6
		Surgical menopause	20.6
17	Natural source that can combat estrogen deficiency is?	Soya been	6.3
		Spinach	17.5
		Carrot	38.1
		Don't know	38.1
18	Hot flushes during menopause can be decreased by?	Sunflower oil	6.3
		Almond oil	12.7
		Olive oil	77.8
		Flaxseed oil	3.2
19	Hot flushes during menopause can be curable with?	Yoga	11.1
		Warm bath	22.2
		Vitamin supplement	23.8
		Air conditioning	76.2
20	During menopause, breathing exercises helps to regulate?	Frigidity	17.5
		Body temperature	47.6
		Bone strength	1.6
		Blood pressure	76.2
21	Good dietary source of iron?	Dates	68.3
		Biscuits	1.6
		Wheat	30.2
		Suppota	0.00
22	Vitamin which can be used to reduce vaginal dryness is?	Vitamin E	4.8
		Vitamin B	28.6
		Vitamin D	34.9
		Don't know	31.7
23	To get enough calcium during menopause, take lot of?	Dairy products	88.9
		Vegetables and fruits	11.1
		Oil products	0.00
		Meat products	0.00
24	Best exercise during menopausal stage of a women's life is?	Swimming	3.2
		Skipping	25.4
		Walking	71.4

		50m run	0.00
25	Milder symptoms of menopausal depression can be relieved by?	10min physical activity/ week 20 min physical activity/ week 30 min physical activity/ week 40 min physical activity/ week	6.3 33.3 15.9 44.4
26	Home remedy for sexual dysfunction during menopause is?	Medication Surgery Family counselling Intimacy with partner	33.3 3.2 23.8 39.7
27	Insomnia during menopause can be reduced by?	Caffeine Nicotine Daily exercise Use of beverages	19.0 1.6 44.4 34.9
28	To improve sleep during menopause, limit fluid intake in the?	Morning Noon Evening Night	1.6 1.6 11.1 85.7
29	For menopausal depressive client, Nervous system is balanced by?	Meditation Sedentary life style Medicine surgery	4.8 60.3 33.3 1.6
30	Nature's best tranquiliser to treat menopausal depression is?	Eating Exercise Trait Maturity	31.7 66.7 1.6 0.00
31	Most effective way to treat symptoms of menopause is?	Hormone therapy Physiotherapy Immune therapy Don't know	3.2 11.1 14.3 71.4
32	Burning and vaginal pain after intercourse can be relieved by the following, except?	Sitz bath Warm water pack Cold pack Don't know	3.2 74.6 4.8 17.5

Average post interventional mean of knowledge of menopausal women about menopausal problems and its remedies in the form of mean is mentioned in table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Post-Interventional Knowledge of Women

Sr No	Knowledge of Menopausal Women	Category	Percentage
1	The word menopause literally means?	Absence of menstruation Suppression of menopause Irregularity in monthly cycle Onset of menstruation	93.7 6.3 0.00 0.00
2	The average age of menopause of women is?	45 years 48 years 50 years 55 years	1.6 4.8 92.1 1.6
3	Irregular menstruation prior to menopause is called?	Perimenopause Polymenorrhagia Stoppage of menstruation Dysmenorrhea	90.5 3.2 0.00 6.3
4	Menopause is complete when women do not have a period for about?	6 months 8 months 10 months 12 months	0.00 3.2 1.6 95.2
5	Hormones that helps to control women's menstrual cycle are?	Estrogen and progesterone Thyroid hormone Don't know Oxytocin	82.3 4.8 4.8 8.1
6	The most common acute symptom of menopause is?	Vaginal dryness Hot flushes Fatigue Stressful life events	9.5 88.9 1.6 0.00
7	Hot flush is most pronounced in?	Legs and hands Head and chest Neck and abdomen Toes	1.6 81.0 14.3 3.2
8	Drug which cause more severe and prolonged hot flushes is?	Tamoxifen Paracetamol Mefal spas Don't know	81.0 7.9 0.00 11.1
9	Common symptoms of vaginal dryness include?	Itching Insomnia Weight gain Abdominal pain	88.9 4.8 1.6 4.8
10	Vaginal changes lead to?	Vaginal infection Uterine infection Night sweats None of above	87.3 9.5 1.6 1.6
11	Serious symptom of menopause is?	Hair loss Osteoporosis Digestive problems Allergies	4.8 90.5 4.8 0.00

12	The strong indication of menopausal stage is?	Decrease in sexual desire Decrease in physical activity Increase in physical activity Increase in sexual desire	90.5 9.5 0.00 0.00
13	Cause of menopausal sexual dysfunction is?	Loss of partner Irritability Loss of memory Menopausal changes	11.1 3.2 6.3 79.4
14	One of the reasons for insomnia during menopause is?	Nightmares Hot flush Irrational thinking Memory loss	9.5 84.1 1.6 4.8
15	Leading cause of menopausal depression is?	Anxiety Phobia Stress Tiredness	11.1 0.00 84.1 4.8
16	Risk for depression during menopause is increased due to?	Medication Brain damage Spinal cord surgery Surgical menopause	7.9 1.6 1.6 88.9
17	Natural source that can combat estrogen deficiency is?	Soyabean Spinach Carrot Don't know	85.7 1.6 1.6 11.1
18	Hot flushes during menopause can be decreased by?	Sunflower oil Almond oil Olive oil Flaxseed oil	0.00 0.00 11.1 88.9
19	Hot flushes during menopause can be curable with?	Yoga Warm bath Vitamin supplement Air conditioning	3.2 0.00 85.7 11.1
20	During menopause, breathing exercises helps to regulate?	Frigidity Body temperature Bone strength Blood pressure	4.8 88.9 0.00 6.3
21	Good dietary source of iron?	Dates Biscuits Wheat Suppota	92.1 0.00 7.1 0.00
22	Vitamin which can be used to reduce vaginal dryness is?	Vitamin E Vitamin B Vitamin D Don't know	87.3 4.8 1.6 6.3
23	To get enough calcium during menopause, take lot of?	Dairy products Vegetables and fruits Oil products Meat products	93.7 4.8 0.00 0.00

			1.6
24	Best exercise during menopausal stage of a women's life is?	Swimming Skipping Walking 50m run	0.00 7.9 90.5 1.6
25	Milder symptoms of menopausal depression can be relieved by?	10min physical activity/ week 20 min physical activity/ week 30 min physical activity/ week 40 min physical activity/ week	0.00 4.8 88.9 6.3
26	Home remedy for sexual dysfunction during menopause is?	Medication Surgery Family counselling Intimacy with partner	7.9 3.2 4.8 84.1
27	Insomnia during menopause can be reduced by?	Caffeine Nicotine Daily exercise Use of beverages	7.9 1.6 85.7 4.8
28	To improve sleep during menopause, limit fluid intake in the?	Morning Noon Evening Night	0.00 3.2 88.9 7.9
29	For menopausal depressive client, Nervous system is balanced by?	Meditation Sedentary life style Medicine surgery	88.9 4.8 6.3 0.00
30	Nature's best tranquiliser to treat menopausal depression is?	Eating Exercise Trait Maturity	12.7 87.3 0.00 0.00
31	Most effective way to treat symptoms of menopause is?	Hormone therapy Physiotherapy Immune therapy Don't know	68.3 4.8 9.5 17.5
32	Burning and vaginal pain after intercourse can be relieved by the following, except?	Sitz bath Warm water pack Cold pack Don't know	76.2 14.3 1.6 7.9

Normality of data is shown in table 4.3. The significance value of Kolmogorov-Smirnova test of normality is 0.84 and value of Shapiro Wilk of normality is 0.64. both values are greater than 0.05 which is an evidence that data is normally distributed.

Table 4.4: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Difference-means	.145	32	.084	.938	32	.064

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The results of paired t test are shown in table 4.5. P value of pre and post-test knowledge scores of women is 0.01 which is less than 0.05 that shows a significant difference in pre and post knowledge scores of respondents. The statistical value is evidence that the structured teaching program was effective in enhancing the knowledge of women about menopausal problems and its remedies.

Table 4.5.1: Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Post-data Pre-data	32	.465	.007

Table4.5.2: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Post.data Pre.data	-.615	.192	.034	-.684	-.546	-18.133	31	.001

DISCUSSION:

Menopause is considered as an emerging health issue of midlife women, where there is gradual shift from reproductive to non-reproductive roles (Mehta, 2017). More women spend a large proportion of their lives in the menopausal state with an increase in expectancy of life (AlQuaiz, ab Salwa, & Habibac, 2013). Physical, social and psychological problems are prevalent in the menopausal women which is a matter of concern and cannot be ignored (Sreeranjini, 2018).

The present study aimed to investigate the effect of structured teaching program on knowledge of menopausal problems among menopausal women between 41 to 60 years old. The study showed that almost all of the women know the what is menopause but they have poor knowledge about menopausal problems and its remedies. A study reveals that women had little knowledge about many major menopausal problems but most had heard of a menopause. Low knowledge of menopausal problems is common for women around the world (Rajbhandari *et al.*, 2017).

Menopause is a natural event in every woman's life and there is no way to escape. In the present study, it was found that women were unaware of the remedial measures used to manage menopause. Most of them admitted never taking any preventive measures during menopause transition as they were unaware of basic preventive measures. This finding of my study is supported by another study which showed each woman who suffered with menopausal symptoms did not practice preventive health behaviors, seek medical consultation, perform physical exercise or had taken any other remedial measure to relieve the symptoms (AbdulHalim, Mehras, Assabri, Alkobaty, & Albourhi, 2018). Other researchers reported similar observations that majority of the studied women had inadequate information about remedial measures and concept of management (Elkazeh & El-Zeftawy).

This research revealed that there is a significant difference in knowledge of women regarding menopausal problems and its remedial measures before and after administration of Structured Teaching Program. The study findings were quite similar to a study; difference between pretest score on knowledge, attitude and practice on posttest score showed that after the educational intervention women begin to adopt health promoting behaviours. As a result, menopausal symptoms significantly decreased in women. The researcher recommended that structured teaching programs should be conducted in order to increase women knowledge about menopausal problems and their management (Shijina, 2017).

After the analysis of the means of pre and post intervention, paired t-test showed the significance value which is 0.001. This value proves that there is an effect of structured teaching program on knowledge of women regarding menopausal symptoms and its remedies. As other researchers described in their study, teaching sessions are not only effective in promoting healthy behaviors but also in reducing menopausal symptoms and complications. Such studies support to detect the common problems faced by menopausal women (Nazari et al., 2016). Awareness to public about menopause and its management to deal with the unique problems of menopause can be done through community health services. Special attention to menopausal women might help women to lead a healthy and fruitful life at menopause (Subrahmanyam & Padmaja, 2016).

CONCLUSION:

Pre-test showed that mean pre-test knowledge of women about menopausal health problems was inadequate. The women had little knowledge on the management of menopausal problems through remedial measures. Administration of structured teaching program was effective in improving the knowledge of menopausal women. The overall mean post-test knowledge of women was found higher as compared to pre-test mean. A paired t test result indicated a significant difference between pre and post-test knowledge score ($p < 0.05$). Hence, it can be inferred that structured teaching program is effective in enhancement of knowledge of the menopausal women regarding menopausal symptoms and its remedial measures. The study concluded that there is a need to educate menopausal women to promote healthy life style.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Limitations:

The sample size was limited to only to 63 menopausal women between 41-65 years of age which is not a true representative of knowledge of all women in Pakistan. Hence, generalization is possible only to the selected settings.

Duration of study was short. Due to time constraint and the sample availability a convenience sampling technique was used in the present study.

Randomization was not done. So, the sample may not be the true representation of the population.

Recommendations:

The same study could be conducted on a large scale to generalize the results.

The study can be conducted in different setting with similar facilities.

An experimental and control group study can be done with similar settings.

A similar study can be carried out to evaluate the effectiveness of several educational approaches like self-instructional module, brochures, booklets and computer-assisted instruction on knowledge regarding menopausal problems and its remedial measures.

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